

Chromatography of synthetic dyes on mixed sorbent layers

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Thin layer chromatography of synthetic dyes has been performed on mixed sorbent layers containing silica gel G, calcium sulfate and barium sulfate separately in ethanol + water (80 : 20) solvent system. The separation potential of admixtures has been explored systematically. Several important separations of closely related synthetic dyes have been achieved.

Separation, identification and quantification of dyes have great importance in separation science¹. The separation of dyes are difficult because of spots tailing and close hR_f values. To encounter this problem silica gel impregnated with organic and inorganic substances^{2,3}, egg shell layers⁴

have been used for the separation of synthetic dyes while RP-TIC has been used for the separation of fluorescent dyes⁵. The survey of literature reveals that alkaline earth salts have high potential for the separation of organic compounds. The sulfates of calcium and barium are highly in-

Fig. 1. hR_f values of various dyes vs different coatings in ethanol-water (80 : 20) system : (A) plain silica gel G, (B) admixture of silica gel G and barium sulfate (80 : 20), (C) admixture of silica gel G and barium sulfate (60 : 40), (D) admixture of silica gel G and barium sulfate (40 : 60), and (E) admixture of silica gel G and barium sulfate (20 : 80).

soluble, non-toxic, cheap and chemically inert material^{6,7} and have been used for the separation of phenols⁶, herbicides⁸, sulpha drugs⁹ and pharmaceuticals¹⁰. The synthetic dyes can not be separated on silica gel G, calcium sulfate and barium sulfate alone. The admixtures of silica gel G with calcium sulfate and barium sulfate have shown the compact spots and the better resolution possibilities in aqueous ethanol system. This paper reports the results of separation of synthetic dyes.

Results and discussion

The following dyes were studied : crystal violet (CrV), gentian violet (GnV), hematoxylin (Hm), bismark brown (Bb), lacmoid (La), resorcinol blue (Rb), Fuschin basic (Fb), amidoswartz (As), Curcumin S (CrS), eriochrome black T (EBT), bromophenol blue (BrB), brilliant green (BrG), safranin (S), orange G (OrG), pan S (PS), methyl red (MR), naphthol green B (NgB), eosin (E), bromothymol blue (BtB), indigo carmine (IC), rhodamine B (RH), methyl violet (MV), alizarin red S (ArS), sudan black (SB).

The hR_f values of various dyes (Fig. 1) reveal that structure of the dyes plays an important role in migration process³, the dyes having two hydroxyl groups, i.e. Rb and ArS show low hR_f values with the exception of CrS and EBT either due to the formation of complexes or due to the high solubility of these dyes in ethanol and water respectively^{12,13}, which give streak and not adsorbed; while on calcium sulfate admixed layers, SB, ArS, EBT and CrS form complexes with calcium and show low hR_f values. The dyes containing one OH groups show slight decrease in hR_f values from coating A to coating E due to hydrogen bonding with the solvent with the exception of PS which shows sharp decrease. IC is insoluble in ethanol and slightly soluble in water¹³ and show streak. BtB is highly soluble in ethanol and move freely. Bb is readily soluble in ethanol and moderately soluble in water and show streak due to steric effect and solvation. The dyes having many benzene ring or of high molecular weight show streak with the exception of MR. BrG and S are of bright color dyes and show similar behavior, i.e. give high hR_f value on plain silica gel G, but as the percentage of barium sulfate increases, the R_f values of these dyes decrease perhaps due to adsorption on barium sulfate layers while these dyes show reversal behavior on the calcium sulfate admixed layers. As, BrG, E, OrG and PS show decrease in hR_f values on coating A to E and reversal behavior from coatings F to I. On the basis of the hR_f value, various separations of analytical importance have been achieved. The separated dyes can be extracted from the layer with 90% ethanol and can be quantized from synthetic and natural samples by simple

spectrophotometric method¹³. The admixture of silica gel G and barium sulfate were more selective and suitable in comparison to the calcium sulfate layers.

Conclusively, the separation of various dyes depends on the following factors : (i) adsorption, hydrogen bonding as well as ion exchange behavior of the dyes on different coatings; steric effect is also responsible in some cases, and (ii) differential solubilities of dyes in ethanol and water.

Experimental

A Stahl apparatus with a universal applicator (adjustable thickness of the applied layer from 0.25 to 2.00 mm), hot air electric drier, glass plates (15 × 3), glass jars (20 × 5 cm), graduated micropipette with vaccupet control and temperature controlled electric oven (Jindal) were used. Silica gel G, barium sulfate, calcium sulfate ethanol (all E. Merck) and the dyes (B.D.H.) were used. Other reagents were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of plates : Plates (0.25 mm thickness) were prepared using a slurry of silica gel G and barium sulfate, and silica gel G with calcium sulfate in different ratios separately in distilled water (DW). The plates were first allowed to dry at room temperature and then at 110° for 1 h in an air-oven. The following coatings were applied to thin layer chromatoplates : Coating A : 30 g plain silica gel G + 75 ml DW; Coating B : 24 g silica gel G + 6 g barium sulfate + 80 ml DW; Coating C : 18 g silica gel G + 12 g barium sulfate + 70 ml DW; Coating D : 12 g silica gel G + 18 g barium sulfate + 65 ml DW; Coating E : 6 g silica gel G + 24 g barium sulfate + 65 ml DW; Coating F : 20 g silica gel G + 1.75 g calcium sulfate + 70 ml water; Coating G : 20 g silica gel G + 9 g calcium sulfate + 70 ml water; Coating H : 20 g silica gel G + 23 g calcium sulfate + 75 ml water; Coating I : 20 g silica gel G + 67 g calcium sulfate + 75 ml water.

The solution of synthetic dyes (10^{-3} M) were prepared in ethanol-water (4 : 1, v/v). Dyes were self-visualized.

Procedure : The test solutions (500×10^{-6} mg) were applied to TLC plates, ca 1.5 cm above in lower edge by means of a micropipette. The spots were dried by hot air and the plates were developed with ethanol-water (80 : 20) mobile phase. The solvent ascent was fixed to 10 cm above the point of application. After development, the plates were dried at room temperature and spots were self-visualized. The R_T and R_L values (which are the rear and front limits of the position of spots obtained for dyes) were measured in the usual way³.

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